

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATION OF INDIVIDUALS WITH DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES

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Abstract. *Modern society, in the light of the increasingly high demands on the education system, has long realized the inherent connection of improving the quality of education with the informatization of the educational process.*

Informatization is considered today as one of the main ways to modernize the education system. This is due not only to the development of technology and technology, but also, above all, to the changes that are caused by the development of the information society, in which the main value is information and the ability to work with it, the development of projects and programs that contribute to the formation of a person in modern society.

Keywords: *children with disabilities, special education, social adaptation, computer simulators, special computer programs.*

The basic principle of the educational environment for children with disabilities is the ability of each child to adapt to the individual needs of different categories of children through flexible adaptation taking into account their individual educational needs.

The educational environment of children with disabilities is characterized by a system of values of reading, upbringing and personal development of all children, resources (means, internal and external conditions) for the formation of their education. A flexible and individual approach to creating special conditions for the upbringing and education of a child with disabilities is one of the indicators of the effective work of the teaching staff.

The educational environment of children with disabilities is characterized by a value system of reading, upbringing and personal development of all children, as well as resources (means, internal and external conditions) for the formation of their education. A flexible and individual approach to creating special conditions for the upbringing and education of a child with disabilities is one of the indicators of the effective work of the teaching staff.

Requirements for physical and technical conditions include the following requirements:

- the organization of an educational institution, including its architectural comfort and universal design, in which the basic general education programs are adjusted;
- organization of a temporary training program;
- technical means of training;
- special textbooks, workbooks, teaching materials, computer-based learning tools that meet the special educational needs of students and complement the selected version of the program.

Each participant of the educational process should be able to use organizational methods or a specialized organizational resource center. Provides material and technical support, including a network of specialists of various profiles involved in the educational process, parents (legal representatives) of the student with HIA, coordination and interaction.

Logistical requirements are aimed at all participants of the educational process. All participants in the educational process should be able to use organizational methods or a specialized resource center. Profiles of different profiles involved in the educational process provide logistical support, including networking, coordination and interaction with parents (legal representatives) of a student with a disability. If necessary, to organize distance learning, specialists will receive a full set of computer and peripheral equipment.

Conditions should be created for the functioning of a modern information and educational environment, including electronic computing resources, electronic educational resources, a complex of information technologies, telecommunications technologies, related technical means (including flash cards, wiki tools, digital video, etc.), everyone should ensure the maximum possible results from the development of this organization and has the right to use distance learning technologies.

The variety of special educational needs of children with disabilities determines the significant variability of special educational conditions, which are distributed across various areas of resources (logistics, including architectural, personnel, information, program and methodological conditions, etc.).

Experimental indicators of the results of the formation of sound reproduction and the development of auditory perception using a specialized computer simulator "I read, I speak".

Fig. 1 - Computer simulator "I read, I talk"

Diagram No. 1

Diagram No. 2

Thus, it is possible to characterize an integral system of special learning conditions - from general situations necessary for all categories of children with disabilities in accordance with their educational characteristics and abilities, to individual situations that determine the effectiveness of the educational process and social adaptation of the child.

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